

THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN CLIMATE DISCUSSIONS

Abstract

This article examines the significant role of the English language in climate change discourse and its broader influence on global environmental communication. English has become the primary medium used in international climate change conferences, scientific publications, and negotiations between countries. The article explores both the benefits and drawbacks of English being the dominant language in this context, while also presenting the views of scientists, linguists, and environmental experts on the subject. English is widely recognized as the global language of diplomacy, international relations, science, business, and transnational cooperation. Its widespread use makes it a convenient tool for uniting diverse nations and experts under a common linguistic framework. Numerous efforts have been made in the past to promote neutral, artificial languages such as Esperanto in order to ensure more linguistic equality in global communication. However, these alternatives failed to gain momentum, and English has remained the central language in most international arenas. There are several reasons why English has become the key language in discussions surrounding climate change. First, it functions as a lingua franca, enabling communication between people from different countries. Second, the vast majority of scientific research, data reports, and environmental policy papers are published in English, giving English speakers greater access to the latest knowledge. Third, most media coverage on climate change—especially in influential global outlets—is also in English, which shapes public perception and understanding. The use of a common language contributes to more efficient communication between policymakers, scientists, activists, and institutions working to address climate-related challenges. It allows for smoother collaboration, easier sharing of technology, and quicker development of joint strategies. However, the dominance of English also raises concerns. It may exclude or marginalize those who do not speak the language fluently, particularly communities from non-Anglophone regions who are often among the most vulnerable to climate change. Ultimately, the prominence of English in climate discussions is not due to its linguistic qualities, but to historical and institutional power structures. This article calls for greater awareness of linguistic inequality in global environmental debates and emphasizes the need to make these discussions more inclusive and accessible for all.

Keywords: *climate change, English proficiency, international language, environmental issues, global efforts*

Introduction

The importance of English in the modern world is difficult to overestimate. It is the international language of communication. According to the Encyclopedia Britannica, there are 1.27 billion native English speakers in the world, making it the most widely spoken language, ahead of Mandarin Chinese and Hindi. English is also recognized as an official language in more than fifty countries [1]. The importance of learning English stems from the fact that it is currently the most widely used lingua franca in international communication in the modern world [2]. This phenomenon can be considered unique for the reason that English is widely used today and is spoken of as the single language of world communication. After the statements of David Crystal, it began to be called a global language [3].

English is the main language that is used in international political relations, diplomacy, science, business and almost any transnational organization. The entertainment industry cannot be ignored: Hollywood and English-language music performers play a key role in global pop culture. Films, TV series, music and books in English have a global audience. The influence of English is so great that many consider knowledge of it a necessity rather than a privilege.

Society has repeatedly tried to find an alternative to the English language. This was done in order to

equalize the chances of representatives of different nations when learning a foreign language. These attempts led to the creation of several new languages, among which Esperanto became the most popular. The author of Esperanto is Laszlo Zamenhof, a linguist from Warsaw. The language was created in 1887, and it took the author 10 years to develop it. However, at a certain point, its development and popularization slowed

Presumably, the reason for this is that the artificially created language has no history, while English has a rich history and deep roots. After all, it was spoken, sung and written by great musicians, poets, philosophers. The role of this foreign language in the modern world is really great. Considering that the world is constantly improving, and in all directions (technology, business, IT industry and others), English has become

a mandatory "attribute" for every specialist in his field.

In this article we touch on the importance of English in discussions regarding climate change, because, as we have already said, most major climate change agreements (like the Paris Agreement), scientific reports (like those from the IPCC), and United Nations climate conferences (COPs) are conducted primarily in English.

Method

One of the main global problems at present is environmental problems with numerous components, including global climate change [4]. By the middle of the 20th century, humanity faced the emergence and rapid development of an environmental crisis on planet Earth. Despite the fact that in the twenty years between the UN conferences in Stockholm (1972) and Rio de Janeiro (1992) 1.2 trillion dollars were spent on environmental protection, the environmental situation on Earth is deteriorating. Thus, in discussions on this topic, English can be considered the key language for several reasons.

Firstly, as we have already said, it is an international language of communication. Secondly, the majority of scientific literature, data, and global media coverage about climate change is published in English. This gives English speakers broader access to the latest findings and discussions.

Thirdly, Effective communication between different politicians, scientists, environmental activists and the public – between countries – often takes place in English. This helps to coordinate efforts, share the latest technologies and build cooperation more effectively.

Results

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) publishes its assessment reports and other documentation mainly in English. This practice ensures that the latest scientific findings are accessible to heads of state, policymakers, scientists and stakeholders worldwide, and contributes to sound decision-making in international climate negotiations. It should be noted that using English as a working language simplifies communication and enhances the effectiveness of the global climate policy framework.

Many prestigious environmental education programs, including those offered by Harvard, MIT, and Stanford, use English as the primary language of instruction. These programs attract students from all over the world, creating a rich international learning environment where cutting-edge solutions to environmental challenges are developed. The use of English in course materials and online platforms creates access to high-quality resources for students from all over the world, regardless of their language backgrounds, which helps to expand global environmental awareness.

Leading environmental organizations and movements such as Greenpeace and Extinction Rebellion primarily operate in English. This common language makes it easier to disseminate information materials, organize global campaigns, and coordinate international action to combat pressing environmental issues. Proficiency in English allows activists to communicate their position effectively, engage with a wider audience, and influence policy at the international level.

These examples illustrate the functional importance of English in facilitating communication, collaboration, and advancing global initiatives to combat climate change and environmental degradation. Despite existing language barriers, the widespread use of English has significantly improved the ability of both individuals and organizations to engage in meaningful environmental debate and action.

Discussions

Above we have indicated the importance of English in discussing environmental issues, mainly climate change. A 2016 study highlights that languages pose a considerable obstacle to the worldwide dissemination of scientific knowledge. The majority of esteemed scientific journals are published in the United Kingdom and the United States. However, it is in the developing world where the most severe impacts of the climate crisis are being experienced [5].

However, there are also some not entirely positive aspects to using English as the main language in various meetings on environmental issues.

For example, an associate professor of English and linguistics Mario Saraceni notes that about 90% of scientific publications are written in English [6]. This represents a significant barrier for the majority of people in the world who do not speak English. He also argues that this linguistic dominance limits the general population's access to important information about climate issues, which in turn hinders global climate literacy and action.

Let's give another example. Miki Mori's study on Mayotte Island indicates that local communities face challenges in addressing climate change due to the absence of appropriate terminology in their native languages. This linguistic barrier hinders effective communication and comprehension of climate-related issues, highlighting the necessity for the development of inclusive language in environmental discussions [7].

The use of English in discussions of environmental and climate issues has some negative consequences, which we have already touched upon above (limited access to information, decreased participation in climate policy). However, if there is one more negative point that is worth paying attention to in this paper - the use of scientific jargon.

The use of scientific jargon in discussions of climate issues can significantly complicate the perception of information by a wide audience. Climate science often operates with complex terms, abstract concepts and statistical models that are understandable to specialists, but not intuitive for ordinary people.

For example, Professor Wendy Bruin de Bruin of the University of Southern California notes that "one of the participants in the study aptly noted: "It seems that you are talking over people." In order to convey findings to a wider audience, it is necessary to move away from scientific jargon and towards simple, understandable language. "In a number of cases, respondents suggested short and clear replacements for complex terms," said Bruin de Bruin. "This showed us that, despite the complexity of the climate change problem, there is no need to artificially complicate it with overly complex vocabulary." [8]

Pete Ogden, Vice-President for energy, climate and environment at the UN, stressed the need to communicate more effectively about the scale of the climate threat to motivate people to take decisive action. "Using accessible and understandable language is key", he said. [9]

Professor Candice Howarth, from the University of Surrey, who specialises in sustainability and climate

communication, points out that the gap between science and practice involves several key areas: culture, language, communication, research methods and the presentation of evidence. She focuses particularly on language and communication, emphasising the importance of avoiding both the overuse of scientific jargon and the oversimplification of scientific concepts that can lead to a loss of scientific rigour. Such carelessness in language often leads to superficial explanations of complex scientific problems, which in turn alienates audiences. Or, at the opposite end of the spectrum, to oversimplification that can undermine the underlying complexities of the response to climate change, leading to potential rebound effects. [10]

These examples highlight the important role of language, particularly English, in shaping global climate debates and the challenges non-English speakers face in accessing and participating in these debates.

Conclusion

Thus, in this article we have explored the crucial role of English in enabling communication, collaboration, and progress in the worldwide effort to combat climate change and ecological damage. It should also be noted that, despite the fact that challenges related to language barriers persist, the widespread use of English has considerably strengthened the ability of both people and organizations to participate in meaningful environmental conversations and initiatives.

The dominance of English in environmental and climate debates is not due to its inherent superiority over other languages, but to historical, political and institutional reasons. On the one hand, it facilitates global coordination, but on the other hand it can also marginalize non-English speakers. Balancing the effectiveness of having a common language with the need for inclusivity is one of the key communication challenges in global environmental efforts.

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